

Exploring the potential of generative design for concept design development in architecture

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Abstract

In the Architecture, Engineering, and Construction (AEC) industry, the early stages of project development hold paramount importance, shaping the trajectory of design outcomes. As the industry embraces technological advancements, integrating generative design approaches emerges as a promising avenue for redefining the design process. The generative design signifies a paradigm shift by automating the generation of numerous design alternatives, enabling data-driven evaluations that drive innovation, streamline processes, and enhance decision-making.

This study delves into the transformative potential of generative design within the initial phases of architectural projects. Early project development demands a delicate balance between imaginative design concepts and pragmatic considerations encompassing feasibility, sustainability, and cost-effectiveness. Through rigorous investigation, this research explores how generative design addresses these imperatives, paving the way for the evolution of established practices. It underscores the pivotal role of generative design in reshaping architectural innovation and aligning design processes with contemporary industry trends.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/0Tp2GA-NKdc>

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